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Empirical Analysis Of The Factors Affecting Women's Participation In Household Financial Decision-Making In Abuja Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study aims to critically examine the factors militating against women's participation in household financial decision-making in Abuja of Nigeria. The dependent variable is participation in household economic decisions. The independent variable is several women's socio-economic characteristics that are prevalent in the Nigerian Society. The study recommended the development of social behavior change through collaboration with religious organizations aimed at encouraging men to allow their wives to take the front role in family financial decision-making. It further recommended for women to earn more income to increase their influence and aid their ability to make strong financial decisions.

Keywords: Gender, Accounting, Household, .Non-Accounting

1.1. INTRODUCTION

All over the world, the issues of female gender in decision making are not widely discussed in literatures. However, studies by Komori (2008), Dambrin and Lambat (2010); Whiting Gammie and Herbohn (2015) have mainly examined the issues as they concerned women at the top echelons of decision making, especially in their decision making ability. According to Abiola and Kabiru (2018), the paucity of literature that addresses the issues of women's gender in financial decision-making may have been responsible for the dominance of their male counterparts in the finance-related professions.

The international conference on women held in Beijing, China in 1995 placed the issues of the female gender on the front burner, leading to the creation of a global platform that call for greater participation of women at all levels of decision-making, mainly in decisions that directly affects women and their children's welfare (Abiola and Kabiru 2018). Economic, Political, and Financial decisions- as prominent and distinct as they are, must make the issue of gender disparity, equality, and inequality a topmost agenda as part of engendering the emancipation of the women race.

For instance, in Nigeria, women are being marginalized in political and national leadership, with very few women in critical decision-making positions. Apart from Mrs. Virginia Etiaba, who accidentally became a governor in Anambra state after the illegal impeachment of former governor, Mr. Peter Obi, no woman to date has become a democratically elected state governor in Nigeria. It is also no longer news that in most Nigerian societies and communities, cultural practices and social norms strongly discriminate against women (Abiola and Kabiru 2018). According to the National Population Commission (NPC) (2004) as cited in Abiola and Kabiru (2018), cultural practices such as wife inheritance, genital mutilations, forced

and early marriages wife battery, and other harmful practices are among the evils committed against female gender in recent times in Nigeria.

Moreover, Kitz and Makinwa–Adebusoye (1999) opined that social relations at the level of the households are not different as many women are not involved in decisions that affect even their health. In most households, the partner with the higher income is often the one who takes most decisions, especially financial decisions (Volger 2008); Layard (2005) believes that wives should be allowed to have access to economic resources through paid employment, to be able to participate in financial decisions making in households. When the husband controlled the finances and or made the financial decisions alone, both the husband and wife would not be as happy in their relationship compared to when responsibilities were shared among them. According to Uwakwe (2004); and British Council (2012), most Nigerian women are not allowed to participate in the labor force. This has further impoverished women and denied them the opportunity to improve their financial, social and welfare status.

Accordingly, one main aspect of the average Nigerian family where discrimination against women has been upheld socially is the sustained participation in household financial decisions, mainly decisions that affect large household purchases. Several researchers including Baba, Zain, Idris and Sanni (2015), and Lamidi (2016), have revealed evidence that household financial decisions have been largely dominated by men across the globe. In an investigation carried out by Edwin and Pramud (2010), it was discovered that women’s autonomy in decision-making is positively associated with their age, employment, and number of living children. Studies in other parts of the world, mainly in developing economies have also revealed a similar lack of housewife autonomy in household financial decisions (Rammohoran and Johor 2009). According to Christina (2004), mothers who contribute to the household’s financial decisions have a strong influence in their families and communities. In the same vein, great number of studies have examined women’s financial autonomy within Nigerian households. The objectives of this study are thus to assess variations in women’s participation in household financial decisions and identify the prediction of women’s participation in household financial decisions across the six area councils of the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.

2.1. Evaluating Women’s Involvement in Household Financial Decisions

Household decisions can be analyzed in various dimensions (Makinwa, 1999). Household financial decisions involve making financial decisions regarding Education, health and major purchases, consumption, and savings plans (Cornish, 2021). Some of these decisions are linked to societal norms while others mainly rely on monetary or financial indications (Schubert, 1999). Women’s role and their involvement in household financial decisions can be judged based on the responsibilities accorded to them in these decisions. Below is a table showcasing the indications and the indicators of managing financial resources by women

	The Margin of Managing Financial Resources
Indications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial Independence • Authority to utilize and spend family resources (for example: renting a family-owned house, selling a family-owned plot, etc. • Authority to manage expenditures • Authority to make health-related expenditures • Authority to spend on children’s education fees • Authority to make general family household purchases etc.

2.2. Non-Accounting Determinants of Women’s Involvement in Household Financial Decision Making

i. The Age of Women

In many theoretical models of Economics, age plays a key role. As a general principle, as humans grow in age, their responsibilities induce them to be more involved in financial decision-making. The case is not different for women, as women get mature with their age, they are naturally inclined to take more interest in household financial level decisions. According to Thapa and

Guvung (2010); and Brajesh and Shekhar (2015) women's involvement in household financial decisions should increase with their age.

ii. Women Employment status

Women's involvement in household financial decision-making and their autonomy rely on many factors mainly, the employment status of women's central role in this regard (Murphy-Graham, 2008, 2010; Sadania, 2016; Bulte 2016). Employed women as compared to unemployed women can be more involved in household financial decision-making based on two reasons: Firstly, their professional experience and external exposure have a great impact on their decision-making ability. According to Dacosta (2008), as women are meant to make many independent decisions in their workplaces, they potentially apply the same at their household levels. Secondly, their employment status allows them to have a reasonable stake in the financial matters of their family, therefore their families provide them some margin to be involved in household financial decisions (Sultana (2013); Sadania 2016). One can fully say that women who are employed rather than unemployed are likely to be more involved in household financial decisions.

iii. Education Level of Women

The Education of women is more the less an important variable among the chain of determinants. Education broadens our minds and always allows us to be more practical and substantive in our lives. This physical feature of education cannot be ignored when it comes to analyzing women's participation in financial decision-making.

iv. Household Size

Our family domain offers a potential reason for our participation and interest in practical matters of our life. A household accords a special role to each of its comprising units and this role can vary with the size of the household. We can physically become more influential and participative within a bigger household size because many more decisions are supposed to be taken in a bigger family domain as compared to a smaller family. Women are more likely to participate in financial decision-making in larger families compared to smaller family groups.

2.3 Accounting Factors Affecting Women's Participation in Financial Decision Making

i. Income of women

Income offers us an opportunity to make effective and independent decisions in our lives. Even within an agglomeration or a joint family set up income is impulsive in increasing our participation in decision making. Hypothetically, income provides a natural impetus for someone to be involved in household financial decision-making; the case must be considered as same for the income of women within a household (Sadina, 2016; Sultana 2013 and Hung 2012)

ii. Financial Literacy Level of Women

Financial literacy entails women's understanding of the financial system and how to take advantage of the system for their benefit. Financial knowledge matters a lot because it has implications for financial decision-making and ultimately financial wellbeing and resilience. Venilia (2024) explained that financial knowledge and confidence matter when making financial decisions. Those women with less financial knowledge and confidence are less likely to make strong financial decisions. It is further noted that women with positive financial knowledge could build stronger financial resilience and are more likely to make positive financial decisions. (Vanilia, 2024)

2.4. Theories of Household Decision Making

A unitary model and the bargaining Power Model within the household stand out in the body of literature on household decision-making.

a) The Unitary Model

The unitary model is a macroeconomic theory of households that assumes that the household unit behaves as a single decision-maker. The household members maximize welfare based on the utility function subject to a budget or financial constraint. The majority of the decisions made are influenced by individual preferences and distinct behaviors of family members in a household

may be independent of one another but to some extent dependent as well. The generalization of the behavior of the household as a single decision-maker made the unitary model unacceptable because of the distinctive features of human behavior and other decisions. This gave rise to the need for a model that would directly incorporate conflict of interest and independent decision-making ability within the household. Thus the bargaining power model.

b) The Bargaining Power Model

This model also known as the bargaining power, is the main feature in a non-unitary model. In simplest words, bargaining means negotiation among household members to advance the common good of the household through agreements and compromises. Negotiation in interspousal communication in the household. So the importance of the bargaining power in this study is about the negotiations that go on within the household for women to arrive at financial decisions regarding household resources and expenses.

3.0. METHODOLOGY

A huge number of women, both housewives and working class in the area of study had a formal understanding of the effect of accounting and non-accounting factors in women financial decisions making.

3.1. Population and Sampling

The population is the total number of persons, objects, or items from which the researcher could draw the study sample. The target population for this study was women in Abuja the Federal Capital Territory of Nigeria. This study also employed a survey research design to achieve the aim of the research.

3.2. Sampling Size Determinant

This study employed judgmental sampling, also called purposive sampling or authoritative sampling, which is a non-probability sampling technique in which the sample members are chosen only based on the researcher’s knowledge and judgment. Because of this, the sample size was allocated according to the six local government councils in Abuja. Each Local Government Area had a sample size of 92, making it a total of 552 respondents.

Sampling process

Local Govt Councils in Abuja.	Urban/Rural Areas of Study	Number of Respondents , Women (House wives and Working Class)
Abuja Municipal Area Council	Garki (Urban)	62
	Apo Village (Rural)	30
Gwagwalada Area Council	Gwagwalada Town (Urban)	62
	Dobi (Rural)	30
Bwari Area Council	Kubwa (Urban)	62
	Barapa (Rural)	30
Kuje Area Council	Kuje Town (Urban)	62
	Pasali (Rural)	30
Kwali Area Council	Kwali Town (Urban)	62
	Leleyi (Rural)	30
Abaji Area Council	Abaji Town (Urban)	62
	Agyana (Rural)	30
Total 6 LGAs	12 Communities/Towns	552

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Questionnaire Distribution Result

Distribution Pattern	Number	Percentage (%)
Questionnaire Distributed	952	100
Questionnaire Retrieved	940	97.8
Questionnaire Not Retrieved	12	2.2
Total		

Source: Field Survey, 2026

For this study, a survey design has been adopted to meet the purpose of the study. It is considered appropriate because it has the advantage of effectiveness in getting information about personal perceptions, feelings, and anticipation. The survey was carried out by the administration of questionnaires to both housewives and working class women in the rural and urban centers of the Six Area Councils of the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. The data generated from this study were subjected to analysis using four (4) Likert scale types and simple percentages.

4.1. Data Analysis

Table 4.1 Responses to research question one.

S/N	Item	SA	A	SD	D	A%	D%
	A woman’s age affects her ability to make financial decisions in family.	290	160	49	41	83.33	16.66
1.	Women’s employment Status significantly affect their financial decision making ability.	30	21	297	192	9.44	90.56
2.	Women’s education level affects their financial decision making.	23	36	157	324	10.92	89.07
3.	Women’s income affect their financial decisions making ability.	215	235	33	57	83.33	16.66
4.	Financial literacy of women significantly affect household financial decision making.	205	270	27	38	87.9	12.03
5.	Professional experience and number children affect women’s financial decision making ability.	63	58	119	288	22.40	77.59
	TOTAL	836	780	682	940		

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Overall percentage

$$\text{Agree} = \frac{1,606}{3,240} \times 100 = 49.56\%$$

$$\text{Disagree} = \frac{1,634}{3,240} \times 100 = 50.43\%$$

4.2. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Data in Table 4.1 above shows the effect of Accounting and Non-Accounting factors on the household financial decisions of women in Abuja.83.33% of the respondents strongly agree that the age of women affect their ability to make household financial decisions, while, 16.66% strongly disagree and hold to the notion that women’s age play no role in the ability of women to make household financial decisions in Abuja.

Furthermore, 90.56% of the respondents disagree with women’s employment status significantly affecting their ability to make household financial decision in Abuja. This implies that irrespective of the

employment status of women, their ability to make household financial decision cannot be affected. Conversely, 9.44% of the respondents are of the view that the employment status of women significantly affect their household financial decision making.

More so, 89.07% of the respondents believe that education level of women has no effect in their ability to make household financial decision in Abuja. This implies that, women are naturally decision makers irrespective of their education background. On the other hand, 10.92% of the respondents are of the view that education level of women affect their household financial decision - making. This implies that education level is not a yardstick to women's household financial decision making.

Furthermore, data in table 4.1 reveal that 83.33% of the respondents agree that women's income level is a strong factor that affect their household financial decision-making. This implies that income level is a major determinant of women' ability to make household financial decisions. However, 16.66% of the respondents disagree with the notion that income level of women determine their household financial decision- making pattern. In addition, 87.9% of the respondents agree that financial literacy significantly affect women's house hold financial decision- making. This implies that financial enlightenment is a very important factor that can trigger women's interest in household financial decisions. On the other hand, 12.03% of the respondents strongly oppose the idea that, financial education is a prerequisite to women's ability to make household financial decisions, especially in Abuja.

77.59% of the respondents disagree that professional experience and, number of children affect women's household financial decision- making level. While, 22.40% strongly support the view that professional experience and number of children affect women's household financial decision level in Abuja.

CONCLUSION

This study reaffirms the fact that there are lot of Factors Affecting women's participation in household financial decisions in Abuja, Nigeria. As observed in this study, the main factors that determine the level of women's participation in household financial decisions are Education level, Age, Women's Employment Status, Income level, Financial Literacy, Professional Experience, and Number of Children. Although these factors are very notable, the society and indeed the men folk ought to encourage women to be financially buoyant in order to contribute their quota to the growth of the family and nation, through responsible household financial decision making.

RECOMMENDATION

The study recommends the following:

1. That women in both the rural and urban setting be encouraged to make financial decisions, especially decisions that will aid them navigate through and survive in a Nigerian economy that is ever dynamic.
2. The study further recommends that women should strive to earn more so as effectively participate in family financial decision making.

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